

ARISTOTELES

OUR FOURTH
NEWSLETTER IS OUT!

ARISTOTELES 4th Newsletter!

Dear reader,

Welcome to the latest edition of the **ARISTOTELES Newsletter**, your biannual source for insights, updates, and highlights from our pioneering project at the intersection of artificial intelligence and personalised medicine.

ARISTOTELES is a groundbreaking project focused on developing **novel artificial intelligence (AI) approaches for personalised medicine**. We're working to create a multinational harmonised data platform that will enable us to better manage complex diseases with multiple interacting pathways. Our goal is to develop personalised AI approaches capable of predicting the risks of comorbidities to shape the future of personalised medicine.

In this issue, we share the latest updates on our work packages, deliverables, recent events, and dissemination activities. You'll also get an exclusive update on our work mapping the Danish National Patient Registry, and we're thrilled to introduce two of our young researchers who are driving innovation within ARISTOTELES, including one new member who has recently joined our team.

Enjoy the read!

The ARISTOTELES Team

Our Coordinator and Principal Investigators

The ARISTOTELES journey continues to advance steadily, and with this fourth newsletter the project moves closer to achieving its ambitious goals. Over the past months, all work packages have entered the active phase of development, marking a significant step forward in the collaborative effort across partners and countries.

Key milestones have already been reached. Europe-wide surveys have been successfully completed, providing valuable insights into clinical needs, care pathways, and current gaps in the management of atrial fibrillation. In parallel, an international data platform has been established, creating a robust foundation on which the ARISTOTELES AI tool will be trained and validated.

Our engineering teams are now fully engaged in the design and development of the tool, working to translate clinical requirements into a reliable, interpretable, and user-centred technological solution. At the same time, clinicians across the consortium are preparing for the implementation of the randomized clinical trial, which will evaluate the tool's real-world impact on patient care.

As ARISTOTELES enters its most dynamic phase, the consortium remains strongly committed to delivering evidence-based innovation that can support healthcare professionals and ultimately improve outcomes for patients with atrial fibrillation.

Prof. Giuseppe Boriani
University of Modena
and Reggio Emilia

Prof. Gregory Lip
University of Liverpool

WP3: SURVEY, DISCUSSION GROUPS AND CO-PRODUCTION

Since our last update, the University of Liverpool, together with our partners, Universities of Crete, Modena, Murcia and 'Carol Davila' Bucharest, distributed two separate surveys, one for patients and members of the public, and one for healthcare professionals (HCPs). The purpose of the surveys was to explore people's knowledge of artificial intelligence (AI) and their perceptions about its' use for healthcare. The surveys produced 558 HCP and 1051 patients and public responses, exceeding the 1600 target. Analysis (ongoing) is focused on both individual country outcomes and an overall set of outcomes across each survey question.

Task 3.2 in WP3 was the delivery of focus groups across each country which have now been completed. Thematic analysis will take place across each country in addition to a combined set of outcomes across all stakeholders. The purpose of the focus groups was to expand on survey answers and develop a greater understanding of stakeholder perspectives, including barriers and facilitators to AI usage.

Task 3.3 in WP3 is the co-design of the AI tool in conjunction with our partners, AI Talentum and LJMU (WP5). AI Talentum have drafted initial AI interfaces for use in the co-production workshops which will involve about 50 people in total (Figure 1).

Figure 1: WP3 will follow a collaborative co-design pathway to co-produce the AI tool interfaces.

The next objectives for WP3 is to finalise the analysis of both the survey and focus group data (December 2025), alongside the completion of the co-design workshops (by April 2026).

WP5 UPDATES – STRATEGIES FOR MISSING DATA IMPUTATION

WP5 has successfully finalised and submitted its second deliverable, **D5.2: Missing Data Imputation**. This deliverable establishes the methodological strategy for handling missing values as a crucial pre-processing component prior to developing the **ARISTOTELES AI risk-prediction models**. The team undertook a detailed review of both traditional and state-of-the-art imputation approaches, followed by an empirical comparison using one of the cohorts selected for model development -adult patients with atrial fibrillation (AF) extracted from the MIMIC-IV database.

D5.2 provides a thorough account of this comparative study. Missing data remain a major source of bias and uncertainty in clinical research, particularly where both **Missing at Random (MAR)** and **Missing Not at Random (MNAR)** mechanisms coexist. To address this, seven imputation methods were evaluated: simple techniques (mean, median, min/max), widely used statistical or distance-based methods (K-Nearest Neighbours, MICE), and advanced deep learning-based generative models (GAIN and DiffPuter).

The evaluation proceeded along two dimensions. First, the statistical fidelity of the imputed datasets was examined using the **Wasserstein distance**, **Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic**, and **L2 correlation-matrix distance**. Second, the practical implications for downstream modelling were assessed by training three predictive models - **Logistic Regression**, **Random Forest**, and **XGBoost** - to estimate one-year mortality and rehospitalisation.

Overall, performance was broadly comparable across methods, although the generative models produced imputations that adhered more closely to the empirical distribution of the observed data. This enhanced fidelity indicates the potential value of generative approaches for complex clinical datasets. At the same time, median imputation proved consistently strong in the predictive tasks, highlighting the importance of balancing modelling performance with statistical realism.

Based on these findings, D5.2 recommends a tailored imputation pipeline for future ARISTOTELES modelling, combining the complementary strengths of three top-performing methods:

- **Median imputation** for its robustness in predictive tasks;
- **DiffPuter** and **GAIN** for their superior preservation of underlying data distributions.

This integrated pipeline is proposed as the project's standard approach, ensuring both accuracy and reliability as subsequent modelling efforts progress.

WP6 – VIRTUAL POPULATIONS OF ATRIAL FIBRILLATION PATIENTS

Work Package 6 (WP6) has successfully completed its first deliverable, **D6.1: Generation of Virtual Populations (VPop) of Atrial Fibrillation (AF) Patients**, submitted on time. This milestone marks a key step toward establishing the foundations for **in silico clinical trials (ISCTs)** within the ARISTOTELES project.

Deliverable 6.1, corresponding to **Task 6.1** and **Milestone 4**, focuses on implementing a model capable of generating realistic virtual populations of AF patients (see Fig 1). The report describes the full workflow, from model selection and data preparation to virtual population generation and evaluation.

After reviewing several model types for producing synthetic medical data, a **language model-based approach** was selected, tailored to the characteristics of the **ARISTOTELES database**. Due to current computational constraints on the project's data platform, the model was first trained locally using the publicly available **MIMIC-IV** dataset. AF patient records and key clinical features were extracted and harmonized with the ARISTOTELES data structure to ensure seamless future integration.

The resulting model successfully generated a cohort of virtual AF patients. The quality of this **virtual population** was evaluated based on its **statistical similarity** to real patient data and its **privacy-preserving properties**, ensuring no individual patient information is compromised.

This deliverable establishes the **methodological and technical groundwork** for creating realistic and privacy-respecting VPopS of AF patients — a crucial enabler for future ISCT simulations within the ARISTOTELES framework.

MAPPING THE DANISH NATIONAL PATIENT REGISTRY TO THE OMOP COMMON DATA MODEL: A NATIONAL-SCALE DATA HARMONIZATION INITIATIVE

Researchers from Aalborg University, in collaboration with the **Danish Medicines Agency** and the ARISTOTELES EU project, have completed a comprehensive mapping of the **Danish National Patient Registry (DNPR)** to the **OMOP Common Data Model (CDM)**. This systematic transformation encompasses **3.8 billion records** from **11 national registries** covering 9.1 million individuals from 1977 to 2024, achieving 94.7% overall mapping coverage across core clinical domains.

The transformation addressed a persistent challenge in Danish healthcare research: incompatibility between Danish-specific coding systems and international standards. Danish diagnoses use **ICD-10-DK**, procedures employ **SKS classification**, laboratory tests follow **NPU nomenclature**, and medications utilize **ATC codes** with local extensions, none directly compatible with OMOP's standardised vocabularies (SNOMED CT, LOINC, RxNorm).

The research team employed a hybrid methodology combining manual curation by clinical experts, semi-automated tools (Usagi), and Large Language Model-assisted classification. Drug exposure mapping achieved 99.93% coverage (1.34 billion records) through 7,108 curated Varennummer-to-RxNorm mappings. Laboratory measurements reached 99.24% coverage (1.59 billion records) with 528 high-frequency NPU-to-LOINC mappings validated by clinical biochemists. Procedure mapping achieved 93.35% coverage (34.6 million records), while diagnosis mapping reached 89.3% (312.7 million records).

Application of GPT-4 language models classified 113,163 healthcare organizations at \$65.82 total cost, achieving 77% accuracy through few-shot prompting. This showed the AI's potential for large-scale medical terminology mapping while highlighting current limitations compared to expert annotation.

The transformation **enables Danish participation in international OMOP research networks**. Application to atrial fibrillation research identified 366,918 patients with comprehensive longitudinal data, subsequently integrated with European databases for multi-national comparative studies. All mappings and transformation code are publicly available through the **OHDSI Denmark GitHub repository**, enabling community validation and refinement.

This work represents the **first national-scale transformation of Danish healthcare data to OMOP CDM**, establishing infrastructure for precision medicine, large-scale epidemiological studies, and international collaborative research.

RAISING AWARENESS AROUND ARISTOTELES

Participation in conferences, fairs, and multiple events

Screening and Early Diagnosis of Atrial Fibrillation: Can AI Get There First?

As part of its ongoing educational efforts, the **Italian Association of Arrhythmology and Cardiac Pacing (AIAC)** hosted a new edition of its **AIAC Club webinar series**, bringing together numerous Italian experts to discuss the expanding role of artificial intelligence in the management of atrial fibrillation (AF). Dr. Mei participated as both moderator and speaker, guiding an in-depth discussion ranging from early diagnosis to the use of AI technologies inside the electrophysiology lab. During his presentation, he presented the ARISTOTELES project, underlying the multidisciplinary nature of the initiative, which involves clinicians, engineers, data scientists, and industry partners working together to develop AI-enabled tools for AF management.

Dr. Mei highlighted how ARISTOTELES aims to generate high-quality clinical and technological evidence through its dedicated trial, designed to evaluate AI-informed clinical decision making for AF patients. He stressed that the project is expected to deliver actionable data that could soon inform everyday clinical practice, supporting physicians in managing complex comorbidities, refining risk stratification, and improving personalized treatment strategies for patients with AF.

The webinar sparked extensive discussion about the project and its upcoming contributions to real-world cardiology practice, engaging dozens of specialists from across Italy. The high level of participation underscored both the clinical relevance of the topic and the growing interest within the medical community in harnessing AI to improve cardiac care.

86TH EDITION - NATIONAL CONGRESS ITALIAN SOCIETY OF CARDIOLOGY

At the Congresso Nazionale SIC 2025, held on 5 December in Rome, the annual meeting of the Italian Society of Cardiology, bringing together clinicians, researchers, and innovators in cardiovascular medicine, the project coordinator Prof. Giuseppe Boriani delivered an oral presentation entitled **“AI and arrhythmias: what secrets might it reveal?”**. His talk focused on the advantages and limitations of artificial intelligence in the investigation of cardiac arrhythmias, highlighting how AI-based tools can enhance arrhythmia detection, risk stratification, and clinical decision-making, while also addressing current challenges such as data quality, interpretability, and integration into routine clinical practice.

ESC DIGITAL & AI SUMMIT 2025

The Modena team participated in the **ESC Digital & AI Summit 2025**, held in Berlin on 21–22 November, with a **poster presentation** entitled **“Artificial Intelligence in Patients with Atrial Fibrillation for the Management of Comorbidities: The ARISTOTELES Project”**, emphasising the role of AI in clinical decision support. The poster presented the aims and design of the ARISTOTELES project, highlighting how artificial intelligence can support personalized clinical decision-making in patients with atrial fibrillation and multimorbidity by integrating large-scale, real-world clinical data to improve risk stratification, outcomes, and resource optimization across European healthcare systems.

SEMINAR ON AI: PERSPECTIVES IN DECISION-MAKING

On 19 January, a seminar focusing on the **emerging intersections between artificial intelligence and biomedical research** was held at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. The seminar featured a compelling presentation by **Prof. Giuseppe Boriani**, titled **AI: Perspectives in Decision-Making**. In his talk, Prof. Boriani highlighted how AI and clinical medicine are becoming ever more **complementary and interconnected**.

The discussion addressed both the **benefits and limitations of AI in healthcare**, emphasizing the importance of a responsible and informed use of AI tools by medical professionals, defined like **“co-pilot”**, capable of enhancing clinical reasoning and supporting daily decision-making. It is fascinating to consider how **science, technology, and medicine** interact in a dynamic interplay, while the human mind remains the true protagonist of final clinical evaluations. The seminar represented a **stimulating forum for multidisciplinary exchange**, bringing together researchers, engineers, PhD students, physicians and offering a valuable opportunity for dialogue and mutual enrichment.

ARISTOTELES stakeholder community

If you're interested in keeping up-to-date with all the latest developments in ARISTOTELES and AI solutions for personalised medicine, we invite you to join our **ARISTOTELES stakeholder community**.

We are excited to share these stories and updates, bringing you closer to the heart of ARISTOTELES and its community. Stay tuned!

ARISTOTELES the interviews

Meet the People Behind ARISTOTELES

Over the past few months, we have shared a dedicated video interview series that brings you closer to the researchers behind the ARISTOTELES project. Through these short interviews, members of the consortium talk about what drives their passion for research, what they value most in their work, and how they see their role in shaping the future of healthcare.

The series is designed to showcase the human side of science, highlighting the motivations, insights, and personal stories of the people working to make cardiovascular care more precise, predictive, and patient-centred.

Let's get to know the people behind the project — click [here](#) to watch the interviews on our YouTube channel!

Meet ARISTOTELES' young researchers!

Jovana Dobreva

From North Macedonia to Denmark: Embracing new horizons in AI-driven healthcare research through data management, ontologies, and the ARISTOTELES consortium. Jovana is our new researcher who joined the Aalborg team in September 2025.

I recently joined Aalborg University as a Research Assistant, focusing on Data Management and Ontologies in Health Care, and this represents one of the most exciting milestones in my life and career. Moving to Denmark and joining the ARISTOTELES consortium is, without question, my greatest achievement so far. It's both a professional opportunity and a personal adventure that I'm incredibly grateful for.

My research journey began during my undergraduate studies in Computer Science in North Macedonia, where I fell in love with the potential of artificial intelligence to transform healthcare. Throughout my PhD and professional experience, I've worked on developing AI systems, from multilingual chatbots to NLP models for medical applications, always driven by the belief that technology can make healthcare more accessible and effective.

What excites me most about ARISTOTELES is the chance to work alongside brilliant researchers across Europe, contributing to personalized risk assessment and clinical decision support systems that will genuinely impact patient care. The project embodies everything I'm passionate about: collaborative research, innovative AI applications, and meaningful healthcare solutions.

I look forward to this new chapter and to contributing to a project that bridges cutting-edge technology with real clinical needs.

Biostatistician, Prost Doctoral Research Associate in Public Health and Epidemiology at the School of Medicine of the University of Crete, Greece.

Marilena Anastasaki

As part of ARISTOTELES in Greece, I coordinate the implementation of all research studies and ensure their successful integration within local contexts. My work focuses on analysing the Greek data to address questions that reflect our country's specific priorities and complexities.

Coming from a background in Mathematics and Biostatistics, the elegance of mathematical structure and the clarity of quantitative thinking sparked my curiosity about how data and numbers reflect human health, behaviour and societies. What fascinates me most about my work is the way Biostatistics, Epidemiology and Implementation Science converge to address real-world health issues and how evidence becomes meaningful for patients' lives.

The biggest challenges in my research have been navigating interdisciplinary barriers and ensuring that rigorous methods translate into sustainable and implementable solutions. In ARISTOTELES, I'm looking forward to work with international colleagues for creating tangible models that empower patients and practitioners. By fostering shared methodologies and real-world validation, ARISTOTELES supports my goal of transforming research into scalable healthcare innovations.

In the next years I would like to see my field move towards genuinely integrated, equity-oriented health research, with data meeting community voices, prevention and lifestyle becoming central in clinical pathways, and methodological sophistication resulting in meaningful impact for underserved populations.

ARISTOTELES

Thanks for your attention!

Be sure to follow us on social media to keep upon all the latest ARISTOTELES news!

CONTACT US

secretariat@aristoteles-horizon.eu

Partners

ARISTOTELES is Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Grant Agreement n.101080189